
Shorinji Kempo Basic Technique Training Model for The Visually Impaired

Agung Wibowo¹, Rumpis Agus Sudarko², Endang Rini Sukanti³, Awan Hariono⁴

^{1,2,3,4}Faculty of Sports Science and Health, Yogyakarta State University

ABSTRACT: This research and development aims to develop a basic Shorinji Kempo training model tailored for individuals with visual impairments, with a focus on improving their basic technical and affective aspects. The background of this research shows that individuals with visual impairments often experience a lack of confidence in social interactions and sports, and there is no specific Shorinji Kempo training model for them, especially in juho techniques. The methodology used was the Borg & Gall Research and Development (R&D) model, modified into six steps: preliminary study and data collection, planning, initial product development, initial testing, product revision, and dissemination. Data was collected through observation, interviews, questionnaires, and literature studies. The initial product was validated by five experts (two training experts, two Shorinji Kempo experts, and one media expert). Limited trials involved five Shorinji Kempo trainers and 18 visually impaired kenshi. The results showed that the training model developed was "feasible" based on validation by subject matter experts (86.94%) and media experts (85.82%). All instrument items were valid based on Aikens' V (≥ 0.81). Limited trials also showed the product's feasibility in terms of physical aspects (89.76%), design (89.5%), and usage (88.19%) with an overall average of 89.15%. The effectiveness test using the N-Gain score showed a significant increase in technical mastery, with the tsuki nuki technique showing the highest effectiveness, followed by johaku nuki and kote nuki. Overall, this basic shorinji kempo technique training model for the visually impaired has been proven to be feasible and effective, contributing significantly to improving technical and affective aspects for the visually impaired. This study recommends wider use of the tsuki nuki technique and further analysis to improve the effectiveness of kote nuki.

KEYWORDS: Development, Training Model, Disability, Blindness, Shorinji Kempo

INTRODUCTION

Sports for people with disabilities, also known as adaptive sports or parasports, are sports played by people with disabilities, including physical and intellectual disabilities. Because many sports for people with disabilities are based on existing able-bodied sports, which are modified to meet the needs of people with disabilities, they are sometimes referred to as adapted sports.

Children with special needs are children who, during their development, experience intellectual, social, emotional, and motor impairments and obstacles, requiring learning services tailored to their abilities. The obstacles and impairments experienced by students with special needs limit their ability to participate in the entire physical education program (Taufan et al., 2018).

Visual impairment refers to people with visual disorders, including total blindness and low vision (Praptaningrum, 2020). Due to their limitations, people with visual impairment often lack confidence in interacting with others (Wulandari & Fauziah, 2020). This has an impact on the suboptimal potential of persons with visual impairment, resulting in reduced cognitive and social demands (Rakhmawati, 2018).

As a result of losing or reducing their sense of sight, blind people try to maximize the functions of their other senses, such as touch, smell, hearing, and others (Arimbi, Poppy, Lita, and Wahyana, 2022). Article 31 of Law No. 11 of 2022 on Sports for Persons with Disabilities states that the development and promotion of sports for persons with disabilities shall be carried out and directed as an effort to achieve equality in sports in order to enhance self-confidence, health, fitness, and athletic performance. Shorinji Kempo martial arts is a martial art similar to judo that originated in Japan. Shorinji Kempo has quite a lot of philosophy that directly touches on human life, for example, "conquer yourself before conquering others," love without strength is weakness, strength without love is tyranny (Cynarski, 2018). Basic techniques in martial arts are the main foundation

Shorinji Kempo Basic Technique Training Model for The Visually Impaired

in every branch of the sport (Cynarski, 2016; Szabó, 2013). From the results of observations and field studies, there is no Shorinji Kempo training model for the visually impaired. Therefore, this training model is expected to provide an alternative option for the visually impaired to learn martial arts.

METHOD

This type of research is Research and Development/R&D Borg and Gall (1998). According to Sugiyono (2018, p. 394), Borg and Gall state that research and development is a process/method used to validate and develop products. Before product development is carried out, data collection is first conducted through observation and literature study. Next, a product design is created. The product design that has been validated is tested (field test) for effectiveness. The design used in this study is the "One Group Pre-Test Post-Test Design".

This study was conducted at MTsLB/A Yaketunis, Jl. Parangtritis No.46, Yogyakarta, from August 4 to October 4, 2024, and the effectiveness test was conducted from October 15 to 20, 2024. The population in this study consisted of all 53 visually impaired students at MTsLB/A Yaketunis. The sampling technique used in this study was purposive sampling of 18 children.

Data collection through observation, interviews, and literature review. Expert validation instruments using questionnaires and effectiveness testing with a pretest-posttest design. Data analysis techniques using qualitative descriptive analysis, validity analysis with Aiken's V Analysis, and effectiveness analysis using N-Gain.

RESULT

Descriptive Analysis Results

The bar chart of the observation results shows the need for a basic shorinji kempo training guide for the visually impaired, as presented in Figure 1 below:

Figure 1. Bar Chart of Guidebook Requirements

Normality Test Results

The Shapiro Wilk method was used to test the normality of the data in this study. The summary is presented in Table 1 as follows.

Table 1. Normality Test Results

Group		<i>p-value</i>
Kote Nuki	<i>Pretest</i>	0,824
	<i>Posttest</i>	0,974
Katate Johaku Nuki	<i>Pretest</i>	0,792
	<i>Posttest</i>	0,815
Katate Tsuki Nuki	<i>Pretest</i>	0,797
	<i>Posttest</i>	0,881

Based on Table 1, the normality test results show that the data from all research groups, both at the pretest and posttest, have p -values > 0.05 . In the kote nuki group, the p -value was 0.824 at the pretest and 0.974 at the posttest. In the Katate Johaku

Shorinji Kempo Basic Technique Training Model for The Visually Impaired

Nuki group, the p-value was 0.792 in the pretest and 0.815 in the posttest. Meanwhile, in the Katate Tsuki Nuki group, the p-value was 0.797 in the pretest and 0.881 in the posttest.

Homogeneity Test Result

The homogeneity test is used to test whether the samples are similar, i.e., whether the samples taken from the population are uniform or not. The results of the homogeneity test in Table 2 are as follows:

Table 2. Homogeneity Test Results

Data	Sig.
<i>Kote Nuki</i>	0,830
<i>Katate Johaku Nuki</i>	0,827
<i>Katate Tsuki Nuki</i>	0,122

Based on Table 2, the homogeneity test results show that the data from both research groups have a p-value > 0.05. In the kote nuki group, the p-value was 0.830, in the katate kote nuki group, the p-value was 0.827, and in the katate tsuki nuki group, the p-value was 0.122.

Validity Test Results

The results of the validity test on product content using Aiken's V validity test obtained the following average results.

Table 3. Validity Test Result

Item Number	V Aiken	Provisions	Description
<i>Mean</i>	0.8777	0,81-1	<i>Valid</i>

Based on the validity test results, the V Aiken score was 0.8777, which is within the **valid** range (0.81-1).

Effectiveness Test Results

The following can be seen in Table 4, the results of the effectiveness test using N-Gain data analysis.

Table 4. Effectiveness Test N-Gain

Subject	Pretest	Posttest	N-Gain
<i>Kote Nuki</i>	2.83	8.00	0,72
<i>Katate Johaku Nuki</i>	3.17	8.00	0,72
<i>Katate Tsuki Nuki</i>	3.00	8.33	0,76

Based on the effectiveness test results in Table 4 above, it can be seen that the data on the ability to perform the kote nuki technique (pre-test; mean 2.83 and post-test; mean 8.00, score, 72.32), the katate johaku nuki technique (pre-test; mean 3.17 and post-test; mean 8.00, score, 71.83) and katate tsuki nuki technique (pre-test; mean 3.00 and post-test; mean 8.33, score, 76.37). Therefore, this Shorinji Kempo Basic Technique Training Model Guidebook for the Visually Impaired is effective for use.

DISCUSSION

The results of the study indicate that the training manual for basic shorinji kempo techniques for the visually impaired is feasible. The development stage used the Borg & Gall 10-step method, namely: 1. Preliminary study and data collection, 2. Planning, 3. Initial product development, 4. Initial testing, 5. Product revision, 6. Large-scale testing, 7. Operational product revision, 8. Operational product testing, 9. Final product revision, and 10. Dissemination and implementation of the developed product. Based on the results of the initial design and analysis, the expert assessment of the training manual for basic shorinji kempo techniques for the visually impaired showed that all items were valid, with V Aiken \geq 0.87.

The expert assessment of the material in the training manual for basic shorinji kempo techniques for the visually impaired was 91.94%, which is considered acceptable. The results of the media expert assessment of the Shorinji Kempo basic technique training model coaching guidebook for the visually impaired were 85.82%, which falls into the acceptable category. The results of the limited trial assessment of the Shorinji Kempo basic technique training model coaching guidebook for the visually impaired were 89.15%, which falls into the acceptable category.

Shorinji Kempo Basic Technique Training Model for The Visually Impaired

Based on the results of the effectiveness test, it shows that there is a significant effect of the Shorinji Kempo basic technique training model guidebook for the visually impaired, where technical skills improved significantly after being trained with the guidebook for 10 sessions. The effectiveness test used the N-Gain Score method for three technical groups: kote nuki, johaku nuki, and tsuki nuki. The N-Gain Score was used to evaluate the improvement in learning outcomes based on pre-tests and post-tests. Analysis of Effectiveness Test Results. Kote Nuki, katete johaku nuki, and katate tsuki nuki, the average N Gain Score in percentage format shows the level of increase in effectiveness. Based on the data, these results show that the kote nuki group had a significant increase from the pre-test to the post-test.

According to subject matter experts, the clarity of instructions in the basic shorinji kempo training material for the visually impaired, the accuracy of the selection of training material for shorinji kempo, the accuracy of the language used in explaining the material, and the suitability of the training material to the concepts and material in the book in accordance with the objectives of basic shorinji kempo training for the visually impaired are quite good. In terms of content suitability, the accuracy of the content/concept of basic shorinji kempo techniques for the visually impaired, the depth of training material for shorinji kempo sports for the visually impaired, and the clarity of the material/concept of training for shorinji kempo sports for the visually impaired, the systematics and logic of presentation, the accuracy of animations to clarify the material, the accuracy of image selection in relation to the material, and the ease of understanding the images presented are very feasible and good. The language used is straightforward, communicative, dialogical, and interactive.

According to media experts, the physical size of a book, the conformity of the book size with ISO standards, the conformity of the size with the content of the book, the cover design, and the appearance of layout elements on the front, back, and spine covers should be harmonious, rhythmic, unified, and consistent. A good center point, composition and size of layout elements (title, author, illustrations, logo, etc.) are proportional, balanced and in harmony with the layout of the content (according to the pattern), the colors of the layout elements are harmonious and clarify their function. The font used and the size of the book title are more dominant and proportional than the size of the book and the author's name. The color of the book title contrasts with the background color, and there are not too many font combinations used. The cover illustration on the book depicts the content/teaching material and reveals the character of the object. The shape, color, size, and proportion of the object are in accordance with reality.

The book's layout design is appropriate, as measured by the consistent placement of layout elements based on patterns and clear separation between paragraphs. Layout elements and print areas are proportional. Page margins are proportional, spacing between text and illustrations is appropriate, and the placement of learning activity titles, subtitles, and page numbers does not interfere with comprehension. The placement of illustrations and captions does not interfere with comprehension. The placement of decorations/illustrations as backgrounds does not interfere with the titles, text, and page numbers. The placement of titles, subtitles, illustrations, and captions does not interfere with comprehension. The typography in this book is appropriate, as it does not use too many fonts, and the use of font variations is not excessive. The width of the text layout is normal, the spacing between lines of text is normal, the spacing between letters (kerning) is normal, making it easy to read. The typography in this book also has a clear, consistent, and proportional hierarchy of titles and hyphenation.

Overall, the illustrations are able to convey the meaning/significance of the objects, with accurate and proportional shapes that correspond to reality. The overall presentation of the illustrations is harmonious, creative, and dynamic. According to the trainers' assessment, the physical appearance of the book, the size and thickness of the book, the cover paper material, and the content paper material are very good. In terms of design, the size of the images in the content, the layout of the images in the content, the size of the images on the cover, the layout of the images on the cover, the size of the text on the cover, the layout of the text on the cover, the size of the text in the content, and the layout of the text in the content are all good.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the research and data analysis that has been conducted, the following conclusions have been drawn:

1. The Shorinji Kempo Basic Technique Training Model Book for the Visually Impaired to improve the motor, cognitive, and affective abilities of visually impaired children consists of six types of physical exercises: warm-ups, basic kihon exercises, kumite, and waza technique exercises, as well as affective exercises such as samu-samu. Product specifications include sample training programs along with volume, intensity, and recovery (training dosage).
2. Shorinji Kempo Basic Technique Training Model Book for the Visually Impaired. Based on material expert assessment of 91.94%, media expert assessment of 85.82%, and limited trial assessment of 89.15%.
3. The Shorinji Kempo Basic Technique Training Model Book for the Visually Impaired is effective in improving Kote Nuki technique with a score of 72.32, Katate Johaku Nuki with a score of 71.83, and Katate Tsuki Nuki with a score of 76.37.

Shorinji Kempo Basic Technique Training Model for The Visually Impaired

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The author would like to express his gratitude to the Graduate Program in Sports Coaching Education, Faculty of Sports Science and Health, Yogyakarta State University for the support and facilities provided during this research. We also appreciate the lecturers who have contributed their knowledge in the preparation and guidance of this research. The author hopes that the results of this research will be useful for sports coaching education.

REFERENCES

- 1) Abdillah, N. (2020). Problematika Pendidikan Moral Di Sekolah Dan Upaya Pemecahannya. *ZAHRA: Research and Thought Elementary School of Islam Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.37812/zahra.v1i1.68>
- 2) Akhmad, I., Nugraha, T., & Sembiring, P. (2021). Speed, Agility, and Quickness (SAQ) training of the circuit system: How does it affect kick speed and agility of junior taekwondo athletes, *Journal Sport Area*. [https://doi.org/10.25299/sportarea.2021.vol6\(2\).6433](https://doi.org/10.25299/sportarea.2021.vol6(2).6433)
- 3) Anders, S., De Jong, R., Beck, C., Haynes, J. D., & Ethofer, T. (2016). A neural link between affective understanding and interpersonal attraction. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1516191113>.
- 4) Anyżewska, A., Dzierżanowski, I., Woźniak, A., Leonkiewicz, M., & Wawrzyniak, A (2018). Rapid weight loss and dietary inadequacies among martial arts practitioners from Poland. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph15112476>.
- 5) Arimbi, Poppy Elisano Arfanda, Lita Puspita, Wahyana Mujari Wahid. 2022. Implementasi Ilmu Keolahragaan dalam Perkembangan Olahraga Disabilitas Indonesia. Jawa Tengah: PT. Nasya Expanding Management.
- 6) Bandy, J., Harbin, M. B., & Thurber, A. (2021). Teaching race and racial justice: Developing students' cognitive and affective understanding. *Teaching and Learning Inquiry*. <https://doi.org/10.20343/Teachlearninqu.9.1.10>.
- 7) Budiadnyana, A. A. N. (2013). Pengembangan Model Latihan Fisik Trx (Training Resistance Extend) Pada Cabang Olahraga Beladiri Shorinji Kempo Tingkat Pelajar. *Journal of Chemical Information and Modeling*.
- 8) Cynarski, W. J. (2016). The Meaning Of Self-Defence: An Expert Definition. A Contribution To The Theory Of Selfdefence And Combat. *Proceedings Of The 10th International Conference On Kinanthropology: Sport And Quality Of Life*.
- 9) Demorest, R. A., Koutures, C., LaBella, C. R., Brooks, M. A., Diamond, A., Hennrikus, W., LaBotz, M., Logan, K., Loud, K. J., Moffatt, K. A., Nemeth, B., Pengel, B., Peterson, A., Brenner, J. S., Kelly, A. K. W., Gregory, A. J. M., Halstead, M. E., Bernhardt, D., Jayanthi, N. A., ... Emanuel, A. (2016). Youth participation and injury risk in martial arts. *Pediatrics*. <https://doi.org/10.1542/peds.2016-3022>
- 10) Doshin So. (1973). *Shorinji Kempo*. Second Printing edition.
- 11) Doshin So. (1981). *What is Shorinji Kempo*. Japan Pubns. Inc; 2nd Printing edition.
- 12) Doshin So & Yuuki So. (2017). *This is Shorinji Kempo: Truly valuing love is the epitome of strength*. Futabasha.
- 13) Jakhel, R. (2019). Karate's ambiguity: Traditional martial art or modern combat sport. *Revista de Artes Marciales Asiáticas*. <https://doi.org/10.18002/rama.v14i2s.6000>
- 14) Kinandana, P. A., & Sudiro, A. (2020). Peranan gaya kepemimpinan pelatih terhadap prestasi atlet (studi pada kontingen shorinji kempo kabupaten malang). *Jurnal Ilmiah Mahasiswa FEB Universitas Brawijaya*.
- 15) Martínez, F., Barraza, C., González, N., & González, J. (2016). KAPEAN: Understanding affective states of children with ADHD. *Educational Technology and Society*.
- 16) Moelyadi, A. (2020). Economic Social Cultural Analysis of Sports Coaching Program in East Nusa Tenggara Province. *Journal of Education, Health and Sport*. <https://doi.org/10.12775/jehs.2020.10.01.007>
- 17) Paruntu, G. S., Tangkawang, S., Kaunang, G., & Tulenan, V. (2020). Game Based Education : Shorinji Kempo. 15(2), 127–136.
- 18) Pandarwidi S, A., Siantoro, G., & Khamidi, A. (2020). The Effects of Zigzag Ladder Exercise Crossover Shuffle, In Out Shuffle and Ali Shuffle Against Speed and Agility. *International Journal for Educational and Vocational Studies*. <https://doi.org/10.29103/ijevs.v2i1.2040>
- 19) Praptaningrum, A. (2020). Penerapan materi ajar Audio buat Anak Tunanetra taraf Sekolah Menengah Pertama di Indonesia. *Jurnal Teknologi Pendidikan*, 5(1), 1–19. <http://139.59.120.216/index.php/jtp/arti cle/view/2849/1978>